

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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***Annotation.** The purpose of the article is a theoretical substantiation of the methodology for the formation of lexical skills and abilities of students in teaching a foreign language in the first and second year. The analysis of theoretical approaches helped us to determine the methodological principles in the process of teaching students a foreign language. Language teaching at the first stage should contribute to the components systematic development of foreign language communicative competence, the final formation of which is completed by the graduation, which means the ability and willingness of a specialist to master communication in professional and social life using a foreign language; recognize the need to learn throughout life. In professionally oriented education it is necessary to develop a foreign language course for each industry, which is specific only for this area. skills and abilities that ensure the construction of correct grammatical forms and syntactic constructions. The analysis of this scientific study did not cause controversy.*

***Key words:** communicative competence, linguistic competence, cognitive activity, language education, speech activity, skills, modern methodology.*

Introduction

In today's globalized world there is a growing need for learning a foreign language. Nowadays it's absolutely the must for any specialist in any field of economics, science, culture etc. to know at least one foreign language.

An indispensable condition for the effectiveness of the pedagogical system is to take into account the situation of the functioning of the language being studied as a means of communication and cognition. A good knowledge of Russian (native language) is the most important prerequisite for successful mastery of a foreign language, thanks to which students get the opportunity to fully realize their knowledge and abilities, freely familiarize themselves with the values of domestic and world science and culture. The organization of the educational process based on the philological experience of students contributes to the maximum use of the transposition of their knowledge, skills and abilities, limiting the interference of linguistic systems that contact in their minds. Besides, the implementation of

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interdisciplinary connections between the disciplines of the language cycle should help expand the linguistic horizons of students, enrich their philological experience, and increase interest in learning languages.

It is a well-known fact that the sphere of teaching foreign languages was influenced by the world integration and globalization processes of the last two decades. But, it is quite obvious that in a rapidly changing world, targets are being adjusted, and knowledge of a foreign language may no longer be necessary only for familiarization with a foreign culture or "introduction" into the world economic space, but also for the ability to appreciate and not lose national identity in multicultural communication of the parties. Therefore, language education should serve the purposes of forming a spiritual and moral personality capable of communicating in a foreign language and successfully interacting with representatives of a different cultural and linguistic environment based on basic humanistic values. Therefore, the teaching methodology must also be adjusted. More L.V. Shcherba noted that the methodology of teaching foreign languages depends on the state and structure of society at a given time [7].

Presentation of the main material of the article.

The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate the methodology for the formation of students' lexical skills and abilities in teaching English in the first and second year. It can be argued that teaching professional foreign language vocabulary to students at the first stage will be more effective if the methodology for the formation of lexical skills and abilities is implemented in a specially designed set of exercises and tasks, as well as teaching English will be carried out on the basis of a specially designed integrated course that will make it possible to arrange intersubject links of disciplines. Modern methodology considers speech activity as a leading aspect in the practical orientation of training. Speech activity is a kind of human communicative activity, which is carried out with the help of special sign systems. Like other types of human activity, it has its own structure and content. Speech activity is an active, purposeful process of transmitting or receiving a message, mediated by the language system and conditioned by the situation of communication, that is, the process of production and reception [3], and, like any activity, is based on appropriate skills and abilities. Two levels are distinguished in the activity structure of a speech utterance – operational and motivational. The operational level consists of speech skills: lexical, pronunciation and grammatical structuring skills. The motivational level of speech utterance is the skill itself. Skill correlates with a speech unit no higher than a phrase, ability correlates with a statement.

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In the process of forming communicative competence, the most important role is given to the development of linguistic competence [8], which consists of grammatical and lexical skills and abilities that ensure the construction of correct grammatical forms and syntactic constructions, the correct use of vocabulary for adequate interaction in the target language. Speech competence, formed when teaching all four types of speech activity, is inextricably linked with lexical skills and abilities, the development process of which underlies teaching vocabulary. The question of the relationship between lexical skills and abilities, their formation and structure remains relevant in the methodology.

Not all scientists believe that skills and abilities may be formed in the process of teaching the lexical aspect of speech. Some researchers (P.B. Gurvich, Yu.A. Kudryashov) analyze only skills (grammatical and lexical). For example, they single out the main ones (the ability to use lexical units in all their characteristic forms and functions, the ability to create lexical combinations of words that have not been encountered in speech experience, the ability to choose a lexical unit according to the situation from a number of opposing ones, close in meaning) and auxiliary ones (the ability to consciously apply lexical knowledge, the ability to create categorical concepts at the level of vocabulary, the ability of lexical paraphrase, the ability to quickly recall words) lexical skills [2]. A.N. Shchukin, define a lexical skill as “an automated action for choosing a lexical unit adequately to the plan and in accordance with the norms of combination with other units in productive speech, as well as automated perception and association with meaning in receptive speech” [1; 8], and does not fix the stage of formation of lexical skills. V.S. Korostelev similarly does not distinguish lexical skill, but characterizes lexical skill as a unit of speech skill and believes that the structure of lexical skill is inseparable from the structure of speech action [4]. What we believe is that in teaching vocabulary, both skills and abilities should be included in the content of training. S.F. Shatilov, giving a linguo-psychological characteristic of lexical skills, divides them into: – expressive lexical skills (skills of intuitively correct word usage and word formation in oral and written speech in accordance with communication situations and communication goals); – receptive lexical skills (recognition and understanding skills in listening and reading lexical phenomena – the structure of the word and its use) and concludes that the lexical skill includes two main components: word usage and word formation [6].

The integrative nature of a lexical unit as the main educational unit requires its multifaceted study, that is, consideration of the sound composition, morphological features, semantic and syntactic compatibility. In this regard, some researchers

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distinguish synthetic lexico-grammatical skills, arguing that the lexical and grammatical aspects of speech act in synthesis, and the word is always grammatically designed and carries certain grammatical information along with semantic information [5]. The lexical correctness of foreign speech depends on the level of formation of lexical skills, i.e. from the strength of the connections of foreign words with concepts and the connections between the words of a foreign language. The decisive factor in correct word usage is the strength and flexibility of these connections. The leading factor in the fight against the interference of the speech skills of the native language is speech practice in the new language, during which strong, flexible speech lexical skills are created that can withstand the interference of the native language [6]. Since the oral and written forms of speech communication implemented in the English language classes are based on a developed lexical mechanism, the actual task in teaching students' professional vocabulary is the formation of lexical skills in close connection with the formation of lexical skills as the basis for the effective development of speech skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing. The components of lexical skill include 1) word formation and 2) word usage. Lexical skills (the ability to use lexical units in all forms and functions characteristic of it and the ability to combine lexical units at the level of derived words and phrases) are gradually formed with the development of the following components: 1) periphrase skills, 2) language guessing skills, 3) translation skills.

The level of proficiency in the lexical side of speech, which is relevant for language learning at the general professional stage, can be determined by the following criteria related to the sphere of the correct choice of a word and word usage: 1) proficiency at the level of automatism in the formation of associative links of a foreign word with the corresponding concept; 2) possession of the semantic structure of a lexical unit, i.e. knowledge of the scope of its meaning in relation to the native language; 3) knowledge of a lexical unit in basic grammatical forms and grammatical-syntactic functions; 4) possession of a lexical unit in terms of syntagmatics.

For the level of vocabulary proficiency of students to meet the specified criteria, it is necessary to rely on the following particular methodological principles in the learning process: 1) the principle of forming at the level of automatism associative links of a foreign word with the corresponding concept; 2) the principle of complex assimilation of all images of the word (graphic, spelling, sound, motor speech); 3) the principle of taking into account the typological features of the word, which consists in the assimilation of its full semantic structure in relation to its correlate in the native

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language; 4) the principle of mastering a lexical unit in terms of paradigmatics, including the development of the grammatical aspect of word usage and in terms of syntagmatics, which implies knowledge of their semantic-categorical and syntactical-categorical behavior. Based on the lexical skills and abilities developed in the process of working on foreign vocabulary as part of a professional English course, students will develop lexical competence. When developing a set of exercises, we used S.F. Shatilov's typology (in the following terminology: language - conditional speech – speech exercises) and on some provisions of the teaching foreign languages theory that are relevant to our educational system.

In accordance with the communicative and practical goals of mastering speech activity in foreign languages S.F. Shatilov reduces all exercises to three types: 1) authentically (naturally) – communicative exercises in which the communicative function of a foreign language is carried out and communication skills are taught; 2) conditionally (educationally) – communicative exercises that imitate and model communication for educational purposes, for students to master the language material, i.e. aspect speech skills; 3) non-communicative exercises (formal, analytical, linguistic) performed in order to comprehend and consciously assimilate linguistic material (grammatical, lexical, phonetic) in various types of speech activity [6]. This classification is recognized as the most successful, although in many methodological publications, both domestic and foreign, the first and the second types of exercises are not distinguished, and the typology includes only two categories: preparatory (non-communicative) and communicative exercises.

Conclusions.

Language teaching at the first stage of education should contribute to the systematic development of the components of foreign language communicative competence, the final formation of which as part of professional competence is completed by the end of university education. It means the ability and readiness of a specialist to master oral and written communication in professional and social life; possession of information technologies and the ability to critically comprehend the flow of information; awareness of the need to learn throughout life.

In professionally oriented education each professional area can have its own foreign language courses specific only to the given area. However, for the general professional stage, foreign language courses should reflect the elements of various professional field.

Accordingly, teaching a foreign language as a mandatory component of the professional training of future specialists also takes place on the basis of a

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competency-based approach. The main goal of language education is the formation of foreign language communicative competence, that is, the ability to communicate in a foreign language with representatives of a different culture.

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